

GUIDE FOR THE CARE OF YOUNG ADULTS WITH DEPRESSION AND THALASSEMIA

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Introduction

Thalassemia is an inherited blood disorder characterized by chronic hemolytic anemia caused by defective hemoglobin synthesis. As a result, the red blood cells in individuals with thalassemia have a shortened lifespan, lasting less than the normal 120 days.¹⁻⁴ According to the World Health Organization (WHO), thalassemia ranks as the most common genetic disease worldwide and is considered a global health concern.²

This genetic disorder is common in regions known as the thalassemia belt, which includes Mediterranean countries such as Italy, Greece, and Cyprus; Southeast Asian countries like Thailand, Cambodia, and Indonesia; as well as Turkey, Iran, and India.³ Geographic disparities in the prevalence of thalassemia demonstrate that this genetic disorder affects populations worldwide, regardless of a country's level of development. For example, in Indonesia, nearly 11,000 adolescents were reported to be living with thalassemia in 2021. Similarly, in the

United States, approximately 4.5% of the population is affected by the condition. Additionally, Egypt has around 11,000 individuals diagnosed with thalassemia.⁴

The global prevalence of beta-thalassemia carriers varies widely, with rates ranging from 1% to 19% across different populations. In Southeast Asia, carrier rates are estimated to be between 3% and 9%, with countries such as Thailand (3-9%), Malaysia (1-4.5%), and Indonesia (around 3%) being among the most affected. In Indonesia, approximately 2,500 new cases of thalassemia are reported each year, and the total number of registered patients has risen significantly from 4,896 in 2012 to 9,028 in 2018.⁵ WHO data indicate that around 250 million people (4.5% of the world's population) are carriers of the thalassemia gene, with 80-90 million individuals specifically carrying this gene.² These figures highlight that thalassemia is a global health concern occurring in both developed and developing

nations, indicating that the incidence of the disease is not necessarily influenced by a country's socioeconomic progress.⁴

Patients with thalassemia commonly present with general symptoms such as anemia, pallor, fatigue, and reduced haemoglobin levels, along with spleen enlargement and Cooley's facies. The latter is a condition where excessive red blood cell production that causes the bone marrow cavity to expand, is leading to bone thinning and forehead protrusion. Splenomegaly and Cooley's facies are signs of ineffective erythropoiesis, where the production of mature red blood cells is insufficient. Clinical symptoms often appear before the child reaches one year of age, typically manifesting as symptomatic anemia between 6 and 12 months, accompanied by decreased levels of fetal haemoglobin. Patients with β -thalassemia major usually experience symptoms such as weakness, easy fatigue, jaundice (yellowing of the skin and sclera), dark urine, rapid heartbeat, shortness of breath, dizziness, headaches, growth delays, weight loss, abdominal swelling due to hepatosplenomegaly, and characteristic facial features including frontal bossing, a crooked (rodent-like) mouth, slightly pursed lips, and dental malocclusion.²

Blood transfusion remains the sole life-saving intervention in thalassemia, with the therapeutic objective of maintaining hemoglobin concentrations within the range of 9–10 g/dl.¹² The diagnosis of thalassemia imposes significant psychological and social burdens on affected patients and their families, attributable to factors such as decreased life expectancy in patients who are non-compliant with regular transfusion regimens, the necessity for lifelong transfusion therapy, and pronounced physical deformities.^{2,6} These challenges contribute to both so-

matic and psychological sequelae. Physically, patients may exhibit skin hyperpigmentation, pallor, alopecia, and abdominal distension secondary to organomegaly. Psychologically, affected individuals frequently report feelings of fatigue, emotional exhaustion, and despair. Furthermore, patients with thalassemia often experience social isolation, activity restrictions, diminished academic achievement, and decreased self-esteem.² The chronic nature of the condition influences overall well-being and daily functioning. Thalassemia, as a chronic disease, inherently affects the sufferer's quality of life. The quality of life for individuals with chronic illnesses is often closely linked to family support, which can place considerable stress on family members, particularly parents, due to the increased care demands.²

Summarizing Individuals living with thalassemia encounter numerous challenges throughout their lives, including the symptoms of the disease, complications and associated chronic conditions, as well as treatment-related difficulties such as painful injections and frequent hospital visits for blood transfusions.³

Anxiety is common among individuals with thalassemia. As a chronic illness, thalassemia can lead to feelings of anxiety and worry similar to other long-term diseases. Adolescents and adults living with thalassemia often face the aforementioned numerous physical challenges, which contribute to increased stress levels. This stress can be a significant source of anxiety. Additionally, anxiety may stem from repeated blood transfusions, fear of death, concerns about family planning, negative thoughts, and various emotional experiences associated with the condition. Depression is also prevalent in patients with thalassemia. The rates of depression among adults with the condition vary widely depending on factors such as study design, assessment tools, and

geographic location. Depression is a mental health disorder characterized by changes in cognition, mood, behavior, and physical well-being, often arising from the chronic nature of thalassemia and its long-term treatment. There is a bidirectional relationship between depression and thalassemia: patients experiencing depression often report greater fatigue, pain, discomfort, and sleep disturbances, while depression itself negatively impacts both the physical and mental health of individuals with thalassemia. This association can contribute to increased morbidity and mortality due to reduced treatment adherence. Consequently, it is recommended that all patients with thalassemia be screened for depression to facilitate timely and appropriate interventions.³

Genetic factors may contribute to the development of depression in individuals with thalassemia. Studies have suggested a possible genetic predisposition for depression located on chromosome 11, near the gene responsible for thalassemia. Furthermore, one of the human tryptophan hydroxylase genes (TPH1), found on the short arm of chromosome 11, plays a key role as a rate-limiting enzyme in serotonin synthesis and is associated with depressive symptoms. The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis responds to depression by increasing basal cortisol levels, which can worsen depressive symptoms and disease progression. Conversely, iron toxicity can disrupt the HPA axis, resulting in decreased levels of ACTH.³

Gender influences the likelihood of identifying and diagnosing mental health conditions. Females are more prone to various psychological disorders, and their traditional role as family caregivers often adds to the challenges and stress they experience. The gap between societal gender role expectations and individual needs can contribute to psychological distress. Generally, psychological disorders such as

depression and anxiety are more common among females. However, one study conducted in Palestine found that males reported higher levels of depression than females. This difference was attributed to the increased social pressures on males in that population, including expectations related to marriage, economic success, education, and family responsibilities.³

Assertiveness is an important concept for patients with thalassaemia major. Patients view assertiveness as the ability to introduce themselves as individuals living with thalassaemia who are capable of working within the limits of their physical condition and treatment regimen, as well as pursuing marriage or education. They explained that assertiveness is a key strategy when interacting with employers, coworkers, classmates, or potential partners. Patients with thalassaemia major often use concealment as a strategy to avoid disease-related stigma stemming from societal misconceptions. However, relying on concealment can lead to physical fatigue, psychological distress such as anxiety and fear of disclosure and reduced access to social support. In contrast, openly identifying oneself as a person with thalassaemia represents the opposite of this concealment strategy.⁷

Patients commonly struggle with body-image concerns including issues related to complexion, facial features, and being underweight or overweight which together contribute to challenges in forming a healthy self-concept. Additionally, their experiences with family, peers, schools, and hospital personnel play a substantial role in shaping these perceptions.⁸ Self-concept constitutes a fundamental psychological construct, and its significance is heightened among individuals living with chronic illnesses, for whom perceptions of identity, capability, and social belonging are often shaped by the ongoing demands

of their condition.⁹

Last but not least, to improve the quality of life for individuals with thalassemia, interventions must involve both the patients and their families. Caregivers, particularly parents, need to be well-informed about thalassemia to effectively fulfill their role as primary caretakers. A lack of knowledge about the disease can lead to suboptimal care. Fostering a sense of security helps patients feel comfortable, calm, and confident in their environment, reducing feelings of fear, shame, and low self-esteem. When patients gain the ability to care for themselves independently, their self-esteem improves, and they may feel hopeful about returning to a healthy state.²

The role of nurse in thalassemia

Nursing care encompasses the entire process from assessment to evaluation. Assessments must be thorough, addressing physical, psychological, spiritual, cultural, and social dimensions. Interventions include maintaining effective breathing, ensuring adequate tissue perfusion, enhancing activity tolerance, improving body image, preventing infections, and supporting growth and development appropriate to the patient's age. Thus, nurses must adopt a holistic approach to enhance the overall quality of life for individuals with thalassemia.^{2,10-20}

While nursing interventions often focus on managing physical symptoms, psychological factors also significantly influence quality of life. Therefore, nurses need to implement strategies that address both physical and psychological needs. It is well documented that thalassemia patients experience a broad spectrum of psychological issues and impaired health-related quality of life. Many may develop anxiety and depression due to social challenges, including uncertainty about the future and restricted social interactions.³

Patients are vulnerable to feelings of hopelessness and other psychological challenges, with some facing the serious risk of suicidal ideation. As primary caregivers who maintain frequent and close interactions with patients, nurses hold a vital responsibility in providing holistic and compassionate care. Therefore, it is essential that nurses possess a thorough understanding of comprehensive nursing practices aimed at enhancing the overall quality of life for individuals living with thalassemia.^{4,5}

Nurses play a crucial role in providing comprehensive care. Their first responsibility is promotive, involving health education for caregivers of patients with hematological disorders, especially thalassemia. The second role is preventive, where nurses take actions to avoid new complications, such as infections. The third role is curative, involving collaboration with healthcare teams to deliver treatments like pain relief and antibiotics. The fourth role is rehabilitative, supporting patients to regain independence and resume normal activities post-treatment.²

The recommendation for nurses depends on their role:^{4,10-20}

- **Promotive Role:** Provide health education to patients and caregivers
- **Preventive Role:** Implement actions to prevent the occurrence of new health problems, such as infection control measures
- **Curative Role:** Collaborate with healthcare teams to deliver nursing care that includes pain relief and administration of treatments to manage and prevent complications

- **Rehabilitative Role:** Support patients in regaining independence and assist them in returning to their normal daily activities after treatment or hospitalization

**Key Recommendations-
General in thalassemia**

The following provide the general guidelines intended to offer a broad overview.

These recommendations serve as a foundation for more detailed and individualized care plans for young adult patients:

- Implement regular screening and prevention strategies for mental health disorders in patients with thalassemia as part of comprehensive care
- Provide comprehensive nursing care by actively involving their parents or caregivers in the care process
- Establish honest, open, and trusting relationships to facilitate discussions about their fears, worries, and challenges
- Conduct thorough patient assessments to ensure nursing interventions are tailored to the individual needs
- Address multiple dimensions of care including physical, psychological, social, cultural, and spiritual aspects to support the holistic well-being of patients
- Recognize and be sensitive to the emotional challenges they face when discussing their illness, offering appropriate support and empathy
- Guide and support parents or caregivers in understanding and performing appropriate self-care in thalassemia
- Encourage collaboration between other health care professionals to foster greater involvement and responsibility in managing the condition
- Address knowledge gaps among parents by delivering targeted education about thalassemia care to enhance their caregiving role
- Focus on holistic care approaches to enhance patient satisfaction, improve quality of

life, and foster a sense of hope throughout the treatment journey

Key Recommendations-Depressed young adults with thalassemia

- 1. Support the maintenance of positive outlook**
 - Development of a friendly environment and open dialogue
 - Offer good quality nursing care, following high quality standards
 - Continuous examination of the patient's mood and outlook
- 2. Continuous support and communication**
 - Explore their way of life, encourage conversation, mental and spiritual pursuits
 - Encourage socialisation, entertainment and connection with support groups and associations
 - Use of technology and establish a help phone-line
- 3. Safe blood transfusions**
 - Maintain safe quality blood transfusion standards
 - Patient safety
 - Provide support during the transfusion process
- 4. Locate and deal with potential problems in safe blood supply**
 - Identify on time any problems with the safe supply of blood
 - Work with volunteer organisations and organise community blood drives
 - Establish and effective collaboration with the local blood transfusion department and

maintain contact with other departments nationwide

5. Assess the role of gender

- Recognize that gender influences on the detection and diagnosis of mental health disorders
- Provide targeted support for females, who are more susceptible to psychological disorders
- Consider the impact of societal gender role expectations and work to reduce psychological distress caused by these discrepancies
- Adopt a gender-sensitive approach in healthcare by recognizing socio-biological factors and understanding how gender differences affect health outcomes
- Tailor mental health interventions to account for gender-specific factors influencing psychological well-being

6. Assess the role of age

- Ensure timely identification of their needs
- Provide interventions to support and promote age-appropriate developmental milestones
- Collaborate closely with parents or family members
- Encourage family involvement in the care process to achieve optimal outcomes in meeting developmental-age goals

7. Enhance Mental Health

- Implement psychological programs led by nurses to address and improve the mental health
- Incorporate meditation therapy as an inter-

vention to help them manage anxiety associated with their condition

- Utilize mindfulness therapy techniques to enhance hope and overall quality of life
- Encourage to focus on positive psychological aspects to reduce negative thoughts and foster a more optimistic outlook on their illness
- Promote psychological support strategies that contribute to higher quality of life by reinforcing positive mental and emotional well-being
- Prioritize early recognition of changes in physical appearance, as body image issues and bodily changes significantly impact the mental health of young adults with thalassemia
- Monitor for early signs of mental health concerns, such as social isolation or missed work, to provide timely and appropriate support
- Identify and address challenges related to navigating the mental healthcare system, recognizing that bureaucratic barriers can negatively affect patients' mental well-being
- Advocate for continuous quality improvement within the healthcare system to reduce obstacles and enhance the patient experience for young adults with thalassemia

8. Provide Educational and Counselling Interventions

- Implement educational programs led by nurses to enhance knowledge about thalassemia, which can empower them to improve their self-care and overall quality of life
- Ensure health education covers comprehen-

sive information, including disease definitions, contributing factors, and strategies for independent care, to build patient confidence and promote autonomy

- Provide counseling programs for both adolescents with thalassemia and their parents to address emotional concerns and reduce stress, anxiety, and fear related to the condition
- Use counseling sessions to facilitate open communication, helping adolescents and their families express their feelings and challenges, which can lead to improved self-esteem and coping skills
- Incorporate problem-solving approaches during counseling to help them manage difficulties effectively

9. Promoting Independent Care: Self-Care

- Implement self-care models to enhance their ability to manage their own care independently
- Provide education and guidance to both adolescents and their parents to empower them in effectively caring for thalassemia
- Encourage to actively participate in self-care practices, as this has been linked to improved quality of life
- Involve parents in the self-care process to offer support and accompany them throughout their treatment journey
- Reinforce the relationship between self-care abilities and quality of life, emphasizing the importance of fostering independence in disease management
- Re-assess the acquired knowledge regarding self-care and the level of treatment adherence

- In cases of self-care failure, organize education and provide written material

11. Recognition of problems associated with the healthcare system

- Observing and systematically record problems with bureaucracy
- Explore and report on patient satisfaction by surveys and interviews
- Continuous quality improvement of the care pathway for these patients

12. Enhancing Quality of Life for caregivers of patients with Thalassemia

- Implement positive thinking training programs to equip parents with effective coping strategies for managing stress and anxiety associated with caring
- Promote Family Empowerment Programs (FEP) to strengthen family functioning and support through increased understanding and active involvement in disease management
- Provide counseling services, both digitally and through traditional means, to enhance parents' knowledge and practices related to thalassemia care
- Incorporate educational interventions such as videos, psychoeducation, and dietary guidance to improve health behaviors and overall quality of life for both parents and patients

Encourage a holistic approach that combines psychological support, family empowerment, and education to maximize improvements in the quality of life for families affected by thalassemia.

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